

Development of a HBIM framework for supporting the diagnosis of historical constructions. A case study in the Master Gate of San Francisco (Almeida, Portugal).

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Abstract

This work aims at developing a Historical Building Information Modelling (HBIM) methodology for supporting the diagnosis phase in historical constructions. To this end, the work evaluates the capacity of HBIM for integrating all the data generated during the pre-diagnosis and previous tests. In order to optimize the generation of this model, this work proposes the use of families with low Level of Detail (LoD) and high Level of Information (LoI). It is worth mentioning the development of specific workflows and scripts that allow to exploit the immersiveness of the panoramic images as well as an approach that transform the results obtained in point cloud clustering methods into valid BIM families. The methodology is validated in a representative study case: the Master Gate of San Francisco in Almeida (Portugal). This masonry building suffers relevant degradation processes that compromise its preservation along the time.

Keywords: Historical Building Information Modelling; Non-destructive tests; Minor-destructive tests; Terrestrial laser scanner; Panoramic images; Point cloud processing.

1 Introduction

Building Information Modelling (BIM) has notably increased its relevance and importance in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry in the last couple of decades. Its interoperability and object-oriented nature are key for enhancing the documental efficiency and the data exchange among all the agents that take part in construction projects, that can be extremely complex and involve a large number of members, starting with the design phase and across all their life cycle. The concept of Heritage BIM (HBIM) was introduced by Murphy et al. (2007) as a complete mapping of an entire Cultural Heritage (CH) building. It is, in essence, the application of the BIM methodology to built heritage, focusing not only on obtaining unambiguous documentation of the object geometry, but also relevant information in terms of its historical and artistic value (Rocha and Tomé, 2021). The limitations or problems that are being faced when developing HBIM models are pointed out in recent literature. Angulo-

44 Fornos & Castellano-Román (2020) highlight two specific aspects: the need of having an
45 exhaustive graphic control of the current state of the building to support decision making,
46 and the duplicity or loss of information that is common in CH buildings, that needs to be
47 unified and standardized under a BIM perspective. Moyano et al. (2021) emphasize the
48 difficulty of modelling objects in historic buildings with structural deformations and
49 complex shapes as a HBIM weakness, together with the intensiveness, in terms of
50 resources, of developing BIM representations of CH buildings. These weaknesses are
51 commonly pointed out in recent literature, together with the lack of interoperability
52 between software (Bolognesi and Caffi, 2019), the lack of technical know-how on
53 practitioners for the application of the technologies for HBIM (Adegioriola et al., 2021)
54 or the integration of a varied information from multiple sources such as historical
55 documentation, surveys, diagnostics or monitoring that requires continuous updating
56 (Bruno et al., 2018). However, as stated by Rocha & Tomé (2021), HBIM has the
57 potential to make culture and heritage more available to everyone by democratizing the
58 access to them. The Covid-19 pandemic has been a harsh example of how important the
59 digital access to the culture may be in a context where the mobility or the physical
60 experience of CH are restricted. In that sense, a key application of HBIM will be the use
61 of Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR) to enhance user community interest
62 in cultural tourism (Barazzetti et al., 2015).

63 The integration of new technologies is fundamental for the development of HBIM.
64 Technologies such as remote data surveying make possible to build accurate 3D models
65 of CH buildings that allow high levels of geometric detail. One of the most common
66 technologies that are employed to this end are the laser scanning and the Structure from
67 Motion photogrammetry. In this context, recent literature shows different case studies
68 where as-built HBIM models are developed from remote sensing data sources. Tortosa et
69 al. (2017) carried out a terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) survey of the façade of a historical
70 church and proposed a workflow to develop a HBIM model, that included mesh
71 generation from the raw 3D point clouds, a refinement of that mesh, and an integration
72 on a BIM platform using the software Revit. Brumana et al. (2018) followed a BIM
73 methodology for the restoration of the Basilica di Collemaggio (Italy), developing a
74 HBIM interoperable and cooperative habit among actors of all phases of the restoration
75 process. They introduce the concept of GoG (Grade of Generation) protocols to describe
76 different Levels of Geometry (LoG) in function of the geometry resulting from the laser
77 scans, adopting the logic of traditional Level of Detail (LoD) to the case of architectural
78 heritage restoration. The HBIM paradigm has been already successfully applied to large
79 CH buildings such as cathedrals: Santagati et al. (2021) studied the conservation state of
80 the St. John the Theologian cathedral in Nicosia (Cyprus), acquiring the building with
81 TLS and photogrammetry and developing a parametric 3D model that allows approach to
82 documentation and restoration information following the HBIM methodology. Similarly,
83 Angulo-Fornos & Castellano-Román (2020) and Mora et al. (2021) use HBIM for
84 supporting preventive conservation actions in the façade of the Cathedral of Seville and
85 the Historical Library of Salamanca, both in Spain. They present methodological
86 developments regarding the 3D modelling of the building and integrating a multisource
87 information that improves the application of the preventive conservation plan.

88 All the works previously cited only use the point cloud as a geometrical base for the
89 geometrical modelling of the families. However, the point cloud contains more
90 information that could be used for extracting the current damages of the construction. The
91 works carried out by Del Pozo et al. (2016) or Leronés et al. (2016) exploit the reflectance
92 captured by these sensors for damage mapping, being possible to localize the presence of
93 moistures or biological crusts among other damages. On the other hand, the works carried

94 out by Valero et al. (2019); Wojtkowska, Kedzierski, and Delis (2021) and Sánchez-
95 Aparicio et al. (2018) highlight the possibility of extracting damages related by the
96 geometry of the element (i.e., deformations or material losses) by analysing the
97 geometrical features of the point cloud.

98 Hence, with this context, this paper proposes a HBIM framework for the diagnosis of CH
99 buildings able to integrate not only the data coming from different previous tests in an
100 interoperable language, but also the damages detected from the radiometric and geometric
101 analysis of point clouds. Thanks to this, it will be possible to give a step forward in the
102 complete exploiting of the data contained in the 3D point clouds. This framework is
103 applied in one of the Master Gates of the Almeida Fortress (Portugal): the San Francisco
104 Gate; giving continuity to the previous works carried out on this Gate (Arce et al., 2018;
105 Sánchez-Aparicio et al., 2018). Among the different improvements, we can highlight: i)
106 the use of 360° images as a source for supporting the diagnosis; ii) the development of a
107 HBIM framework for managing the multisource information; iii) the integration of
108 additional tests such as Scanning Electron Microscopy and X-ray diffraction for the
109 material analysis; and iv) the development of BIM routines and scripts able to integrate
110 the data extracted from the analysis of radiometric and geometric features of the point
111 cloud.

112 Under this basis, this work is structured as follows: Section 2 gives a brief historical
113 background and a constructive description of the case study. Then, Section 3 shows the
114 experimental program carried out and describes the employed technologies and analysis
115 techniques for the geometric and material characterization of the Gate. Then, Section 4
116 describes the integration of the geometry and the multi-source information within a HBIM
117 framework, and finally, section 5 draws the conclusions from this work.

118

119 2 Case study: The Master Gate of San Francisco

120 2.1 Historical background

121 The fortification of Almeida (Portugal) consists of six bulwarks, forming an almost
122 perfect 6-pointed star, and it is located in the heart of the historic town of Almeida,
123 near the city of Guarda, Portugal. It is part of the group of Italian-style fortifications that extend
124 along the border area between Spain and Portugal, known as ‘*La Raya*’, where countless
125 territorial disputes have occurred over time (Rosado, 2010) (**Figure 1**).

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Figure 1: Fortifications on the Spanish-Portuguese border.

129 The construction of the Almeida military complex began in 1641 under the direction of
130 the French engineer Antome Delville in response to the fortifications erected in Ciudad
131 Rodrigo and Aldea del Obispo (Fuerte de la Concepción), and in 1657 it was already
132 considered one of the best fortresses in Europe (Albornoz, 2007; Campos, 2009). It is

133 formed by bulwarks, defensive elements that are linked together through the so-called
134 curtain walls. On the outside of the star-shaped polygon formed by the bastions are the
135 six ravelins and the perimeter moat (**Figure 2**).
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Figure 2: General image of the Almeida fort in Portugal.

139 Access to the fortified complex is through two double entrances that begin at the ravelin
140 of San Francisco and Santo Antonio respectively (Campos et al., 2007). The gates that
141 give access to the fortress are: i) the Master Gate of Santo Antonio in the northwest and;
142 ii) the Master Gate of San Francisco in the southeast of the building. These Gates are the
143 most outstanding architectural and decorative elements of the fortress (**Figure 3**).

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Figure 3: Almeida Fortress: a) main infrastructures and; b) main Master Gates. From Cobos and Campos (2013).

147 The construction of the San Francisco gate began between 1661 and 1667 and is attributed
148 to the engineer Pierre Garsin. Throughout its history it has undergone important reforms
149 and reconstructions (Campos et al., 2007). Between 1669 and 1735 the restoration of the
150 Master Gate, which was badly affected by the Portuguese Restoration War, was carried

151 out. In this restoration, the floor plan of the main vault was modified from a rectilinear to
152 a curvilinear plan (the one it shows today), as a result of the new military construction
153 rules. In 1810 the siege of Almeida took place during the Spanish War of Independence,
154 during which the Master Gate was extensively damaged by the constant bombardments,
155 as well as by the explosion of a powder magazine, destroying the access bridge to it. In
156 October 1812 the restoration works began, but they were carried out by unqualified
157 personnel (military prisoners) and were delayed until 1815. In the 30s, after being
158 declared a national monument, the restoration of the fort began. The main doorway was
159 raised and grouted and the stone blocks in the main vault were replaced. In the 60s and
160 70s, restoration work was carried out on the main door, including cleaning of vegetation,
161 grouting of the masonry and construction of its pavement. In 1986 the restoration of the
162 secondary vault took place using a hydrophobic mortar with a composition of
163 approximately 1:2/3:6 (cement : lime : sand). In 1992 the tourist information centre was
164 created inside the secondary vault, providing the space with water and electricity
165 installations, as well as waterproofing the roof. Around 1995, consolidation work was
166 carried out on the stone through cleaning and subsequent inorganic injection of calcium
167 hydroxide at low pressure.

168 **2.2 Constructive description of the building**

169 Located in the southwestern part of the Fort of Almeida, the Master Gate of San Francisco
170 is one of the two entrances to the San Francisco ravelin (**Figure 4**). Constructively, the
171 Master Gate consists of two façades built in granite masonry, where the main façade is
172 outstanding. Along the same, it is possible to observe four Doric columns with a granite
173 ashlar masonry (0.45 x 0.80 cm approximately) cushioned and with ornamental motifs in
174 the form of cylindrical perforations practiced on it. All this decorative set is headed by a
175 great coat of arms of the Portuguese nation where artistic and military motifs are mixed.
176 (**Figure 4**).

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178

179 **Figure 4:** Main door of San Francisco: a) Detail of the capital of the pilaster; b) Detail of the base of the
180 pilaster; c) Coat of arms at the top of the main door. From Cobos (2013).

181 The secondary façade of this Master Gate is more austere, without any ornamental details
182 other than metal window frames, lacking military coats of arms, columns or even
183 decorative mouldings. Crowning both façades, the Gate has a gabled roof erected with a
184 grey granite floor (**Figure 5**).

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Figure 5: Current aspect and state of conservation of the San Francisco Master Gate.

188 Between all these constructive elements (facades and roof) there are two barrel vaults. A
189 main vault with a straight line from the main façade to the middle of the door and a curved
190 trace to the end of the door, with a width of 6.00 m and an average height to the keystone
191 of 6.50 m and another secondary vault of smaller dimensions (4.55 m wide x 5.00 m high)
192 and straight line that runs parallel to the main vault on the west side of the construction
193 (**Figure 6**). Both vaults are connected by an access door and interspersed with small
194 windows with inclined jambs that confirm the type of military architecture to which they
195 belong.

a)

b)

c)

196
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Figure 6: Planimetry of the Master Gate of San Francisco: a) Plan; b) Cross section; c) Longitudinal section.

198 **2.3 Pre-diagnosis of the construction**

199 Before performing the previous test (i.e., geometrical and material characterization), a
200 visual inspection was carried out on the construction with the aim of obtaining a general
201 view about its conservation state.

202

203 This visual inspection allowed to identify numerous damages, both structural and non-
204 structural. In the non-structural category the presence of lichens was identified, especially
205 on the main façade (**Figure 7a**). On the secondary façade, some biological action was
206 also identified, as well as an out-of-plane deformation at the right side (**Figure 7b**).
207 Regarding the vaults, great material losses were observed on the main vaults as well as

208 the presence of large areas with white crust and moistures (**Figure 7c-d**). A different crust
209 appears on the secondary vault (**Figure 7e**), suggesting that the origin of both damages is
210 different. In this vault, large areas with moistures are also observed. On the roof, it is
211 observed the presence of two types of lichens as well as some hole that seems to be linked
212 with a historical event (i.e., a siege). The main structural concerns are the great loss of
213 material in the joints and the loss of material in the granite blocks used for the stone
214 masonry of the main vault.
215

216 **Figure 7:** Visual identification of the damages: a) biological colonization of the main façade; b) out-of-
217 plane deformation of the secondary façade; c) presence of white crust and strong material losses on the
218 main vault; d) presence of moisture and strong material losses on the main vault; and e) white crust on the
219 secondary façade.

220 Additionally to the damage inspection, the pre-diagnosis phase allowed to identify the
221 different types of stone presented in the Gate by means of a visual inspection (**Figure 8**).
222

223 **Figure 8:** Visual identification of the different granites: a) coarse grained grey granite on the secondary
224 façade and on the roof; b) fine grained ochre granite of the main façade; c) coarse grained grey granite
225 on the main façade; d) medium grained ochre granite of the main vault; and e) medium grained ochre granite
226 of the secondary vault.

227 Regarding its history, the works carried out by Arce et al. (2018) have revealed the
228 different relevant events of the Gate, such as the French siege which damaged the Gate
229 or the different restoration actions carried out in the 20th century. During this set of
230 restoration actions, different cement mortars were applied mortar on the masonry, which
231 are the ones promote the presence of melting salts in the secondary vault. For more details
232 on its history, reader is referred to Arce et al. (2018).
233

234 **3 Experimental program: geometrical and material characterization**

235 The data captured during the pre-diagnosis phase revealed a construction with relevant
236 conservation problems due to a large loss of material, moistures, and white crusts among
237 others. In accordance with this, a diagnosis phase was carried out based on the use of
238 several previous tests with the aim of evaluating unknown parameters from the
239 construction and material point of view, including the origin of the damages. This phase
240 was carried out from a multidisciplinary point of view, integrating not only the data
241 captured in previous phases (Arce et al., 2018; Sánchez-Aparicio et al., 2019, 2018) but
242 also generating new knowledge such as the 3D point cloud of the secondary vault or even

243 several X-ray and SEM+EDX tests on the material (stone and mortar) and on the white
244 crusts. The following figure summarized the workflow performed during this phase
245 (**Figure 9**). It is worth mentioning that all the data generated during this phase were
246 translated to an HBIM framework for performing the diagnosis, as it is showed in detail
247 in the following section.
248

249

250 **Figure 9:** The multidisciplinary methodology used for the diagnosis of the Master Gate. In red the tests
251 carried out during the works performed by Arce et al. (2018). In orange the works carried out by Sánchez-
252 Aparicio et al. (2019) In blue the works performed by Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018). In purple the tests
253 carried out during the current work.

254 3.1 Geometrical characterization

255 The external envelope of the construction was characterized by using laser scanning
256 technology. The façades, main vaults and roof of the construction were obtained from the
257 previous experimental campaign (Sánchez-Aparicio et al., 2018). In a similar way that
258 the previous campaign, the secondary vault was digitalized by using a phase-shift laser
259 scanner Faro Focus 120. This laser scanner is able to capture near 976,00 points per
260 second with a nominal accuracy of 2 mm. A total of 3 scan stations were required to
261 digitalize the whole vault. Then, this vault was aligned with the rest of the model by using
262 the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm between overlapped areas. The registration
263 error was 3 mm.

264 The point cloud was coloured by performing one spherical panorama on each scan station.
265 To this end, a reflex camera Nikon D-5600 and a full-frame fisheye lens Nikkor 10.5 mm
266 were employed. Thanks to the field of view of this lens, it was required only to take seven
267 images, 6 in horizontal, each one at 60 degrees and one in nadiral position, for generating
268 the spherical panorama. This acquisition protocol ensures an overlap between shots of

269 about 20-30%. The adverse lighting conditions of the main and secondary vaults
270 demanded the use of the exposure bracketing technique in order to properly acquire the
271 different areas. The shots taken were processed following the approach defined by Brown
272 and Lowe (2007) (**Figure 10**). During this stage a specific mount was used with the aim
273 of aligning the rotation axis of the laser scanner with the pupil entrance of the camera.
274 This device could be consulted in detail in Del Pozo et al. (2019). It is worth mentioning
275 that these products, the panoramas, were used also for enriching the BIM environment
276 due to its intuitiveness and sensation of immersiveness.
277 Result of this, a complete digital replica of the construction was obtained with a total of
278 1,345,405,322 points. This number of points were reduced by using a distance filter of 5
279 mm, giving as a result a 3D point cloud made up by 114,433,234 points (**Figure 11**).
280

281 **Figure 10:** Panoramic images obtained during the experimental campaign: a) secondary façade; and b)
282 main vault.

283
284

285 **Figure 11:** 3D point cloud of the construction: a) general view and; b) detailed view of the roof.

286 The data of the external envelope was complemented by the data obtained by Arce et al.
287 (2018) and Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2019). In the work of Arce et al. (2018) it was decided
288 to use the Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) to evaluate the inner composition of the
289 vertical walls as well as the thickness of the masonry vault. This test revealed that the
290 vertical walls of the vaults have a multi-layer composition made up by a first and third
291 layer of regular masonry wall with 40 cm of thickness. The second leaf was made up by
292 rigid infill. Regarding the vault, the radargrams revealed an average thickness of around
293 35 to 45 cm. On the other hand, the boroscopic test carried out by Sánchez-Aparicio et al.
294 (2019) revealed the inner composition of the main vault on which the roof covering shows
295 20 cm thickness and the infill is made up by natural soil.

296

297 **3.2 Material characterization**

298 During the current campaign it was carried out the following tests: i) four x-ray power
299 diffraction on the stone and mortar of the main vault; and ii) two Scanning Electron
300 Microscopy and Energy Dispersive X-Ray (SEM + EDX) tests on the different white
301 crusts observed on the main and secondary vaults. These tests allow us to have a deeper
302 knowledge about the construction material of the building, complementing the data
303 obtained in previous obtained in previous campaigns which were carried out by Arce et
304 al. (2018) and Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2019). In these campaigns the authors evaluate

305 the Young Modulus and compressive strength of the masonry by using several laboratory
306 and in-situ tests.

307 3.2.1 X-ray power diffraction

308 Four X-ray power diffraction tests were carried out with the aim of obtaining the chemical
309 composition of the construction materials. Three of them on the stone (two from the main
310 vault and another one from the main façade) and another one on the lime mortar of the
311 main vault. In this case the equipment used was the Bruker D8 Advance ECO equipped
312 with a high-sensitivity copper anode and a SOL-X (scintillation counter) solid state
313 energy dispersion detector. The X-ray diffractogram was carried out by using an angular
314 range from 3 to 65 degrees, a step of 0.04 and a time step of 0.5 seconds. Then, a
315 semiquantitative analysis was carried by using the Chung method. The main
316 mineralogical phases detected on the diffractograms of the stone were the quartz, feldspar
317 and plagioclase. Additionally to this phases, the presence of kaolinite and clinocllore was
318 detected. These phases corroborate the disaggregation of the granite.

319 The results obtained in the mortar diffractogram revealed the presence of limestone as the
320 principal mineralogical phase from the carbonatation of the slaked lime. Additionally, it
321 was possible to identify the presence of quartz as the arid of the lime mortar with a ratio
322 lime/quartz of about 1/4. This ratio was obtained by using the intensity ratio algorithm.

323 3.2.2 SEM + EDX tests

324 Apart of the x-ray diffraction tests, the current work performed several SEM + EDX tests.
325 More specifically, these tests were carried out on the following locations: i) on the white
326 crusts of the main vault (Sample A-1); and ii) on the white crusts of the secondary vault
327 (Sample A-7). Sample A-1 revealed that the white crust of the main vault corresponds
328 with the dissolution of the lime mortar since it shows elements related with the Calcium
329 Carbonate (**Figure 12a-b**). Sample A-7 revealed the presence of melting salts (Sodium
330 Carbonate) which are related with the cement mortar used during the last restoration of
331 the secondary vault (**Figure 12c-d**).

332

333
334 **Figure 12:** Results of the SEM + EDX tests: a) and b) represent Sample A-17; c) and d) represent Sample
335 A-10.

336 3.3 Damage mapping

337 The final stage of the experimental campaign comprises the complete damage mapping
338 of the structure. During this stage it was considered the results of the automatic damage
339 inspection carried out by Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018) on the façades and main vault.
340 This damage mapping was complemented by a manual damage mapping which was
341 performed on the secondary vault and roofs with the aim of having a complete image of
342 conservation status of the building. In this case the orthoimages extracted from the
343 combination of laser scanner point clouds and panoramic images were used as a suitable
344 base for mapping (**Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 13**), using the damage classification
345 proposed by ICOMOS (Vergès-Belmin, 2011). All these data, the automatic mapping
346 performed in Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018), as well as the manual mapping carried out
347 during this work were properly integrated into the HBIM framework by using specific
348 scripts.
349

350 **Figure 13:** Manual damage mapping: i) on part of the roof; and ii) on a vertical wall of the secondary
351 vault.

352 4 Integration of the information within a HBIM framework

353 The current section will show the different procedures carried out for defining the HBIM
 354 model of the construction. This stage started with the definition of the different
 355 constructive elements. Then, the damages and the previous tests were inserted with the
 356 aim of carrying out the diagnosis of the construction at the final stage.

357 4.1 Definition of the LoD and LoI of the HBIM model

358 Historic buildings are the result of a series of transformations that they have undergone
 359 throughout their history, so they must be conceived as the product of a sequence of
 360 constructive, destructive and transformative actions. In addition, these buildings are
 361 characterized by the use of materials and construction techniques, in many cases, specific
 362 to each building.

363 In order to adapt the BIM methodology to historic buildings, some important aspects have
 364 to be taken into account, such as the level of detail (LoD) or the level of information
 365 (LoI). The LoD determines the graphical aspect of the building elements, such as
 366 geometry, size or orientation; while the LoI refers to the amount of relevant but non-
 367 graphical information about them, such as material test data and additional images. In
 368 historical buildings the objects have many details that are difficult to model with unique
 369 and non-parametric shapes, especially the ornamental parts, so depending on the purpose
 370 of the HBIM, a different LoD may be necessary. On this basis, the following criteria were
 371 adopted: i) a low LoD and; ii) a high LoI. Table 1 shows the different LoD and LoI
 372 adopted for each family according to the recommendations exposed by Barnes and Davies
 373 (2015), as well as the international guide G202TM - 2013 (G202-2013 Project BIM
 374 Protocol) and the Spanish recommendations exposed in the Spanish Chapter of the BIM
 375 Forum (buildingSMART).

376
 377

Table 1. Level of Detail and Level of Information adopted for each family included in the HBIM model.

Type of object	Level of Detail (LoD)	Level of information (LoI)
Construction elements	300 Elements properly represented in terms of quantity, size, shape, location and orientation	400 Technical system specification, including components to allow product selection
Test	200 Generic system, object, or assembly with approximate quantities, size, shape, location, and orientation	500 Detailed specification of manufacturer's product, testing operation and maintenance
Damages	200 Generic system, object, or assembly with approximate quantities, size, shape, location, and orientation	500 Detailed specification of manufacturer's product, testing operation and maintenance

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In the case of complex geometries (e.g., ornaments) where the adopted LoD implies a simplification of their details, image type fields have been included in the LoI as well as links to the 3D point cloud and to the 360° images through specimens of the previous test family. All this information allows a detailed analysis of these simplified geometries.

384 **4.2 Definition of families: generation of the HBIM model**

385 The following sections will describe the different type of families used within the HBIM
386 model. The families considered were: i) constructive systems; ii) damages and iii)
387 previous tests.
388

389 **4.2.1** *Constructive systems*

390 The first stage for the definition of the BIM model was the modelling of its internal and
391 external envelope. For the external part, data extracted during the experimental campaign
392 carried out by Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018) and Arce et al. (2018) were chosen, in which
393 a laser scanner survey of the building was performed. For the internal definition of the
394 construction systems, the GPR and the boroscopic data obtained in the same campaigns
395 were used. The modelling of these constructive systems was carried out using Autodesk
396 Revit BIM software, creating different types of families and specimens according to the
397 needs of the model. Most of the elements were modelled using native families of the
398 software, such as walls (IfcWall); floors (IfcSlab) or roofs (IfcRoof). In these families,
399 the different layers were defined together with their materials and thicknesses according
400 to the data obtained in the previous studies. In addition, to complete the model, parametric
401 families were created for the French doors, windows, columns, mouldings and singular
402 elements (**Figure 14**).
403

404
405 **Figure 14:** Screenshot captured during the modelling stage. Modelling of parametric families a)
406 vigilance tower; b) column y c) flared entrance door

407 The LoI of these types was defined through the following fields: i) type of constructive
408 technique (IfcText); ii) characteristics of the element (IfcText); iii) date of construction
409 (IfcDate); iv) description (IfcText) and v) date of inspection (IfcDate). Entering this data
410 allows the subsequent filtering and visualization of construction elements according to
411 specific criteria (**Figure 15**).
412

Figure 15: Main façade classified by the type of masonry used.

415 Different materials were assigned to each of the layers of these families according to the
416 pre-diagnosis performed as well as to the data captured and analysed in Sánchez-Aparicio
417 et al. (2018) and Arce et al. (2018). These materials contain information regarding their
418 mechanical and physical properties according to the scheme defined by (Barontini et al.,
419 2021), which are the following: i) stone type (IfcText); ii) stone origin (IfcText); iii) stone
420 density (IfcText); iv) stone compressive strength (IfcText); v) stone tensile strength
421 (IfcText); vi) stone elastic module (IfcText); and vii) stone Poisson ratio.

422 In order to speed up the introduction of new data, and even the modification of some
423 existing data, EXCEL sheets were used. This methodology was used for the modification
424 and introduction of the information contained in all the copies of the model.

425 As a result of this process, it was possible to obtain a geometric model suitable for the
426 diagnosis of the construction and where the ornaments were suppressed while
427 maintaining the basic geometry of each element (shape and layers) (**Figure 16**). The use
428 of these types also allowed an adequate quantification of the different types of masonry
429 (**Figure 17**).

430

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a)

b)

c)

431 **Figure 16:** Geometric modelling used during the present work: a) general view with the 3D point cloud
 432 superimposed; b) general view without the 3D point cloud superimposed; and c) section on the model
 433 where it is possible to observe the different layers of the walls.

Imagen	3_TYPE	3A_NAME	3B_TYPE OF CONSTRUCTIVE TECHNIQUE	3C_CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ELEMENT	3D_DATE OF CONSTRUCTION	3E_DESCRIPTION	3F_DATE OF INSPECTION	Área
MASONRY BETWEEN MAIN AND SECONDARY VAULTS								
	CONSTRUCTION TECHNIQUE	MASONRY BETWEEN MAIN AND SECONDARY VAULTS	REGULAR MASONRY WITH MORTAR	REGULAR OCHRE GRANITE BLOCKS WITH LIME MORTAR	01_01_1668	THREE LEAF REGULAR MASONRY BLOCKS	7_06_2019	60.19 m²
MASONRY BETWEEN MAIN AND SECONDARY VAULTS: 2								
SECONDARY FAÇADE MASONRY								
	CONSTRUCTION TECHNIQUE	SECONDARY FAÇADE MASONRY	REGULAR MASONRY WITH MORTAR	REGULAR GREY GRANITE BLOCKS WITHOUT MORTAR	01_01_1668	TWO-LEAF REGULAR GREY GRANITE BLOCKS WITHOUT MORTAR	7_06_2019	80.76 m²
SECONDARY FAÇADE MASONRY: 1								
ROOF COVERING								
	CONSTRUCTION TECHNIQUE	ROOF COVERING	REGULAR MASONRY	GREY GRANITE BLOCKS RECEIVED WITH CEMENT MORTAR	01_01_1960	GREY GRANITE BLOCKS RECEIVED WITH CEMENT MORTAR	7_06_2019	412.21 m²
ROOF COVERING: 2								

434 **Figure 17:** Planning table with the different types of masonry used.
 435

436 4.2.2 Damages

437 The pre-diagnosis phase revealed the presence of different types of damages along the
 438 construction such as moistures, white crusts, biological colonies or material losses among
 439 others. This plethora of damages are in line with the studies carried out by Sánchez-
 440 Aparicio et al (2018) on which are proposed several point cloud processing strategies
 441 based on the analysis of radiometric and geometric features for the automatic damage
 442 mapping. Based on these results, in the present work, an automatic Dynamo routine
 443 capable of integrating this information into different types of elements within the HBIM
 444 model has been developed. For this purpose, a family of nodes without specific
 445 categorization (generic models) was created to represent each point of the point cloud.
 446 Geometrically it has a sphere shape for its correct visualization and it is modelled with
 447 geometric parameters that allow to modify its dimensions easily at different scales. Based
 448 on this family, a Dynamo routine was programmed to create a sample for each of the
 449 points classified during the multispectral analysis and the CANUPO classifier (at the
 450 corresponding x,y,z spatial position). These nodes are then projected onto the surface of
 451 the building element. Finally, these nodes are classified according to their damage
 452 parameter (**Figure 18**). In this way, the point cloud values are linked to the representation
 453 in the BIM platform (**Figure 19**). Each specimen has a set of fields specific to all
 454 construction damages, which are as follows: i) Type (IfcText); ii) Name (IfcText); iii)
 455 Date_Of_Inspection (IfcDate); iv) Class (IfcText); v) Sub-Class (IfcText); vi) Sub-Sub-
 456 Class (IfcText); vii) Identification (IfcText); viii) Short Description (IfcText); ix) Direct
 457 Causes (IfcText); x) Indirect Causes (IfcText); xi) Associated Damages (IfcText); xii)
 458 Proposed Previous Test (IfcText); xiii) Reparation Proposal (IfcText); xiv) Images
 459 (IfcUrl); xv) Structural Element (IfcText); xvi) Stability_Influence (IfcText); and xvii)
 460 Urgency (IfcText). It should be noted that the Class, Sub-Class and Sub-SubClass
 461 parameters were inherited from the nomenclature proposed by ICOMOS (Vergès-Belmin,
 462 2011).

463 Thanks to the above methodology, it is possible to integrate all the information detected
464 through the analysis of the point cloud into copies compatible with BIM standards and
465 thus allow, through planning tables, their rigorous quantification.
466

467 **Figure 18:** Scripts developed in Dynamo: a) for integrating the damages detected on point clouds; and b)
468 for integrating the damages detected manually

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a)

b)

c)

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Figure 19: Results of the integration of data coming from point cloud processing algorithms into the HBIM model: a) loss of material in the main vault obtained from the CANUPO algorithm applied in Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018); b) presence of incrustations from the leaching of lime mortar in the main vault obtained from the multispectral analysis performed in Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018); and c) visualization of both damages.

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The rest of the damages not classified in the work carried out by Sánchez-Aparicio et al. (2018) were integrated into the BIM model in a semi-automatic way. For this purpose, a path-object family with the capacity of adapting to the host surface was created. The information of this family is assigned through the corresponding parameters (defined below) and entered through an Excel sheet. This methodology was carried out by means of a script developed in Dynamo (**Figure 20**).

1_Efflorescences		3_Soiling		2_Moisture	
Modelos genéricos (1)		Modelos genéricos (1)		Modelos genéricos (1)	
Restricciones		Restricciones		Restricciones	
Cotas		Cotas		Cotas	
Datos de identidad		Datos de identidad		Datos de identidad	
Proceso por fases		Proceso por fases		Proceso por fases	
Datos		Datos		Datos	
1A_NAME	Efflorescences	1A_NAME	Soiling	1A_NAME	Moisture
1B_DATE_OF_INSPECTION	7_06_2019	1B_DATE_OF_INSPECTION	7_06_2019	1B_DATE_OF_INSPECTION	7_06_2019
1C_CLASS	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	1C_CLASS	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	1C_CLASS	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT
1D_SUB-CLASS	Efflorescences	1D_SUB-CLASS	DEPOSIT	1D_SUB-CLASS	MOIST AREA
1E_SUB-SUB-CLASS		1E_SUB-SUB-CLASS		1E_SUB-SUB-CLASS	
1F_IDENTIFICATION	DD_EF_EF	1F_IDENTIFICATION	DD_D_S	1F_IDENTIFICATION	DD_MA
1F_SHORT DESCRIPTION	Efflorescences on the secondary va...	1F_SHORT DESCRIPTION	Dark soiling due to the presence of ...	1F_SHORT DESCRIPTION	Moist area in the main vault due to ...
1G_DIRECT CAUSES	Presence of melting salts in the mor...	1G_DIRECT CAUSES	Presence of water and biological ag...	1G_DIRECT CAUSES	Presence of water
1H_INDIRECT CAUSES	Project and execution causes due to...	1H_INDIRECT CAUSES	Project and execution causes due to...	1H_INDIRECT CAUSES	Project and execution causes due to...
1I_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	Material losses	1I_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES		1I_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	Material losses
1K_PROPOSED PREVIOUS TEST		1K_PROPOSED PREVIOUS TEST		1K_PROPOSED PREVIOUS TEST	
1L_REPARATION PROPOSAL	Cleaning the masonry and applicati...	1L_REPARATION PROPOSAL	Cleaning of the masonry	1L_REPARATION PROPOSAL	Construction of a drainage system
1M_IMAGES	https://tdop.usal.es/Almei...	1M_IMAGES	https://tdop.usal.es/Almei...	1M_IMAGES	https://tdop.usal.es/Almei...
1N_STRUCTURAL ELEMENT	No	1N_STRUCTURAL ELEMENT	No	1N_STRUCTURAL ELEMENT	Yes
1O_STABILITY_INFLUENCE	Low	1O_STABILITY_INFLUENCE	Low	1O_STABILITY_INFLUENCE	Average
1P_URGENCY	Average	1P_URGENCY	Average	1P_URGENCY	High
1R_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	-	1R_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	-	1R_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	ML_ML_DD_E_E
1_TYPE	DAMAGE	1_TYPE	DAMAGE	1_TYPE	DAMAGE

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Figure 20: Damage type specimens integrated into the BIM model manually through the 3D point cloud: a) moisture in the secondary vault; b) efflorescence in the secondary vault. and c) moisture in the secondary vault.

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The visualization and management of these nodes is carried out in the same way as any of the family copies that make up the model, so that the values of the parameters entered allow alphanumeric queries or thematic visualizations through the appropriate filtering of information (**Figure 21**).

DAMAGES									
Image	1C_CLASS	1D_SUB-CLASS	1F_IDENTIFICATION	1F_SHORT DESCRIPTION	1G_DIRECT CAUSES	1H_INDIRECT CAUSES	1L_REPARATION PROPOSAL	1R_ASSOCIATED DAMAGES	AREA
Efflorescences									
	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	Efflorescences	DD_EF_EF	Efflorescences on the secondary vault due to the presence of salt in the mortar used for retrofitting the masonry	Presence of melting salts in the mortar within water that promotes the hydration and deshydration of the salts	Project and execution causes due to the type of mortar used	Cleaning the masonry and application of a lime mortar	-	115.01 m ²
Material losses									
	MATERIAL LOSS	MORTAR LOSS	ML_ML	Mortar losses due to the dissolution of the lime mortar.	Presence of water that promotes the dissolution of the lime	Project and execution causes due to the absence of a drainage system	Cleaning of the masonry and restitution of the lime joints. Also it is necessary to develop a drainage system for the water in order to avoid further crusts	DD_E_E	99.30 m ²
Moisture									
	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	MOIST AREA	DD_MA	Moist area in the main vault due to the absence of a drainage system	Presence of water	Project and execution causes due to the absence of a drainage system	Construction of a drainage system	ML_ML; DD_E_E	27.77 m ²
Soiling									
	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	DEPOSIT	DD_D_S	Dark soiling due to the presence of exogenous particles transported by air and water. This particles give a dirty appearance to the surface of the element	Presence of water and biological agents	Project and execution causes due to the absence of a drainage system	Cleaning of the masonry	-	18.34 m ²
White encrustation									
	DISCOLOURATION AND DEPOSIT	ENCRUSTATION	DD_E_E	White crusts on the main vault of the construction. This damage is due to the dissolution of the lime mortar, reducing the contact area between blocks, increasing the stresses between them.	Presence of water that promotes the dissolution of the lime	Project and execution causes due to the absence of a drainage system	Cleaning of the masonry and restitution of the lime joints. Also it is necessary to develop a drainage system for the water in order to avoid further crusts	ML_ML	0.00 m ²

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Figure 21: Table with the different damages observed in the vaults.

497 **4.2.3 Previous Tests**

498 Previous Tests were represented by customized path-objects as proposed by Sousa et al.
 499 (2018). The path-objects are geometrically simple elements with a low LoD, but with a
 500 very complete LoI. These elements are modelled by Revit families based on generic
 501 models with two basic geometries: i) a sphere shape placed one meter from the ground
 502 for Image 360° and Laser Scanning type tests and ii) a rectangular or circular shape, which
 503 are attached to the walls where the test has been performed, for boroscopic camera, X-
 504 ray diffraction, GPR, ECO-impact tests among others (**Figure 22**). All these families are
 505 modelled by means of geometric parameters that allow to modify their dimensions in a
 506 specific way to give more or less visual relevance (**Figure 23**).

507 To complete the LoI of these families, a series of type parameters have been added from
 508 the corresponding group of general parameters created previously, by means of a routine
 509 in Dynamo that achieves in a simple way to apply these parameters to each type of Revit
 510 family specimen. These type parameters are: Type (IfcText), Name (IfcText), Date of
 511 Acquisition (IfcDate), Date of Processing (IfcDate), Type of Test (IfcText), Equipment
 512 used and set-up (IfcText), Short description of the results obtained (IfcText), Images of
 513 the results (IfcURL), Videos (IfcURL), Metadata of the sample (IfcText) (**Figure 22**).

514 All these data could be consulted in a unique table by using the planification option
 515 (**Figure 24**).

516 **Figure 22:** Detail of the different elements and parameters integrated in the BIM model for representing
 517 the previous tests: a) element and parameters for panoramic images; b) element and parameters for the
 518 laser scanning; c) element and parameters for the X-ray diffraction; and d) element and parameters for the
 519 boroscopic camera.

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a)

b)

520 **Figure 23:** Placement of different elements of the previous test family on the HBIM model. The blue
 521 rectangle represents the X-ray diffraction test on the mortar sample. The green sphere represents the 3D
 522 point clouds. The red sphere represents the 360° images. The pink path of the roof represents the
 523 boroscopic test.

IMAGE	2_TYPE	2A_NAME	2B_DATE_OF ACQUISITION	2C_DATE_OF PROCESSING	2D_TYPE OF TEST	2E_EQUIPMENT USED AND SET-UP	2F_SHORT DESCRIPTION OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED	2G_IMAGES OF THE RESULTS	2I_METADATA OF THE SAMPLE
360 IMAGES									
	PREVIOUS TESTS	360 IMAGES	7_06_2019	10_06_2019	Non-destructive in-situ	Nikon d5600 equipped with a fisheye lens and a panoramic roundabout	Panoramic imágenes for pre-diagnosis	https://tidop.usal.es/Almeida/Previous Tests/images_360.html	-
360 IMAGES: 17									
BOROSCOPIC CAMERA									
	PREVIOUS TESTS	BOROSCOPIC CAMERA	9_08_2019	9_08_2020	Intrusive test in-situ	Drill with glass bit and portable boroscope camera with usb connection to laptop	Thickness of the vault of about 40 cm, granite cover of about 20 cm and natural soil as infill of about 20 cm	https://tidop.usal.es/Almeida/Previous Tests/Boroscopic Camera.html	-
BOROSCOPIC CAMERA: 1									
LASER SCANNER									
	PREVIOUS TESTS	LASER SCANNER	9_08_2019	9_08_2020	Non-destructive in-situ	Laser scanner faro focus 120	3D point cloud of the construction	https://tidop.usal.es/Almeida/point_cloud/index.html	-
LASER SCANNER: 3									
X RAY DIFFRACTION									
	PREVIOUS TESTS	X RAY DIFFRACTION	20_06_2019	20_06_2019	Laboratory test with no sample recovery	Chisel, hammer, diffractometer Bruker D8 Advance ECO	Sample of lime mortar with a ratio (lime/sand) of about 1:4	https://tidop.usal.es/Almeida/Previous Tests/X-Ray Diffraction.html	Alm-R-04-2019
X RAY DIFFRACTION: 3									

524 **Figure 24.** Planning table with the values of the different parameters according to the family type
 525 previous tests.

526 While the images and videos of each of the specimens can be viewed directly through the
 527 URL link, the consultation of the 360° images and the 3D point clouds required the

528 development of a Dynamo routine for their correct visualization. In this routine we
529 implemented a connection with the free software FSP Viewer for 360° images and the
530 Potree library for the 3D point cloud, allowing to consult and exploit in an agile way the
531 information contained in these specimens (**Figure 25**).
532

533 **Figure 25.** Visualization of external sources: a) 3D point cloud and; b) 360° imagery based on a
534 developed Dynamo script.

535 **4.3 Diagnosis**

536 The HBIM platform allows to integrate all the information generated during the diagnosis
537 phase. Thanks to this, it was possible to know the origin of the damage in order to propose
538 a reliable intervention in the Gate. This intervention was articulated in the following
539 proposed actions:

540

- 541 • Main façade: this element is highly affected by biological colonies as well as black
542 crusts which are the results of the biological activity. This damage is in 50% of
543 the façade. Also, a large erosion of the fine-grained granite due to the poor quality
544 of this material was observed. Some in-plane deformations of the columns as well
545 as out-of-plane deformation on the main planes were observed as result of past
546 sieges. Masonry cleaning is recommended.
- 547 • Secondary façade: The presence of biological colonies in lower quantities is
548 observed (20% of the whole area), as well as an out-of-plane deformation in the
549 main plane due to a bad constructive praxis. This deformation represents the 18%
550 of the whole area and does not compromise the stability of the wall, so it is
551 recommended to maintain it.
- 552 • Roof: this is one of the most important elements since it is promoting the water
553 infiltration, the presence of melting salts on the secondary vault and the
554 dissolution of the lime mortar on the main vault. Waterproofing of the system is
555 recommended.

- 556 • Main vault: this constructive element presents important areas on which the lime
557 mortar leaches, as well as important material losses. Both damages are reducing
558 the bearing capacity of the system, since one third of the area of this element is
559 affected by strong material losses. This element is safe but if losses continue,
560 crushing effects could appear due to stress concentration. Replacement of the
561 mortar and some stone elements is recommended.
- 562 • Secondary vault: in this element the most relevant damage are the melting salts.
563 These salts have appeared due to the presence of cement mortar (last restoration),
564 affecting 70% of the element. It is therefore recommended that this mortar be
565 replaced with a compatible lime mortar, as well as cleaning the salts.
566

567 **5 Conclusions**

568 This work aims to take a step forward in the integration of BIM workflows within the
569 diagnosis of historical constructions. This integration is particularly challenging as there
570 is no standardization in terms of families as well as geometric modelling. In this sense the
571 article proposes a set of families with low LoD and high LoI to integrate the
572 multidisciplinary data generated during this phase. It is worth mentioning the
573 development of specific scripts for the integration of different geoinformatics tests. On
574 the one hand, the use of free viewers (FSP Viewer and Potree library) is proposed for the
575 visualization of panoramic images and 3D point clouds, respectively. This proposal is of
576 great interest in the diagnostic phase since it allows us to exploit the accuracy of point
577 clouds (which is partially lost when transformed to a 3D model), as well as the
578 intuitiveness of panoramic images. In our study case the latter is a resource of great
579 relevance since it allows us to check the distribution of the damages or constructive
580 elements among others. Complementary to this, the work develops two Dynamo scripts
581 for integrating the damages into the BIM environment. On the one hand, we propose an
582 approach that takes as inputs the results of the clustering methods and transform it into
583 compatible families. This method opens a new set of possibilities since it enables the
584 connection between the data obtained by different point cloud processing strategies (i.e.
585 multispectral analysis) into BIM environments in an automatic way. The main drawback
586 encountered during this development was the need to subsample the point cloud by
587 distance. This subsampling is motivated by two issues: i) the need to compute the area of
588 damage with the number of points detected in each one; and ii) the need to have a good
589 processing time. Accordingly, a subsampling of 2 cm was used. Thus, 4 points of a given
590 damage represent an area of 4 cm². On the other hand, the work develops a script that
591 allows to quantify damages by attaching specific families into the BIM model.

592 Future work will focus on improving this methodology by introducing vectorization
593 methods such as the convex hull, as well as additional artificial intelligence methods that
594 allow to improve the results of the clustering. These improvements will allow a fast
595 processing time as well as a really accurate quantification of the damage, allowing 4D
596 analysis of damages.

597 With regard to the case study evaluated, the HBIM methodology proves to be an excellent
598 approach for the integration of multi-disciplinary data. Thanks to its interoperability, it is
599 possible to quickly share information in the form of IFC models. The data captured during
600 this experimental campaign together with data from previous campaigns allow us to
601 conclude that the Gate requires short-term intervention due to the presence of different
602 degradation mechanics in the stone. These interventions should focus on the improvement
603 of the drainage system of the vertical façades and the roof, as well as the restitution of the
604 lime mortar, among others.

605

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